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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

POPE PIUS II PICCOLOMINI'S ORIGINAL LETTER ON THE SIBYL'S CAVE PUBLISHED FOR THE FIRST TIME EVER (WITH NEW FINDINGS)¹

1. A fifteenth-century letter on the 'Venusberg'

It is with the greatest pleasure that “The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend” is proud to present to the research community and the general public the most famous letter written by a great Pope, Pius II Piccolomini, on the subject of Mount Sibyl in the first decades of the fifteenth century.

It is the first time ever that the letter is shown in his original manuscripted version, preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (Département des Manuscrits, Latin 8578). The fine script is by the hand of the Pope himself, Enea Silvio Piccolomini, a learned scholar, poet and writer, who decided to copy into a single manuscripted volume all the letters written during the period which preceded his election to Papacy. The volume also contains an elegant miniature showing the Pope as he sits at a scribe's desk of his time (see figure).

But the most interesting aspect is that Letter n. LXXIII in the manuscript contains the original version of the renowned text written by the then thirty-nine-year-old Piccolomini on the Apennine Sibyl. The letter was previously known only from the printed version published in 1551 in Basel.

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(http://www.italianwriter.it/TheApennineSibyl/TheApennineSibyl_SibylsFortune.asp)

And we will see that a couple of new remarkable findings will unexpectedly pop up from the perusal of this original version, never published before.

Fig. 1 - The initial page of Manuscript Latin 8578 preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, containing a series of letters written by Enea Silvio Piccolomini in the first half of the fifteenth century

The Apennine Sibyl. Her mountain and cave, in Italy. A mystery that, during the fifteenth century, was being brought to the attention of a wider audience by the literary works of Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale. An enigma that, according to Felix Hemmerlin, a cleric and essayist who lived in the same period, seemed to have a strong connection with the German legendary tale of Tannhäuser and the Venusberg, the mountain which housed the magical realm of Goddess Venus.

In the first half of the fifteenth century, when his Papacy was still to come, Enea Silvio Piccolomini received a visit from a person who asked him very

peculiar questions. And he decided to write to his beloved brother Gregory to ask for further information. The following is the text of the letter sent by Enea Silvio to his brother on the day of January, 15 1444.

The title of the letter leaves no space for doubts: it's «De Monte Veneris», a direct reference to the legend of Tannhäuser. And to the Italian Sibyl:

«Imperial Secretary Enea Silvio sends many greetings to jurist Gregory, his brother. The bearer of this letter came to me in this very hour asking me a question: whether I know any Mount of Venus be in our land of Italy. In fact he said that knowledge is imparted there of magical arts, of which his master is eager to know, a prominent Saxon astronomer».

Fig. 2 - The opening of Enea Silvio Piccolomini's letter on the 'Venusberg'

[In the original Latin text: «Aeneas Silvius Imperialis Secretarius S.P.D. (salutem plurimam dicit) Gregorio iurisconsulto fratri suo. venit ad me hac hora lator presentium ex me quesitum: an veneris montem apud italiam scirem. Nam ibi magicas artes tradi dicebat, cuius avidus esset herus suus qui Saxo est summus astronomus»].

So somebody, an assistant to an eminent German scholar of the time, was looking for information about a magical mountain that seemed to raise its peak in Italy and was known as the 'Venusberg', which was the very name of the mount that appears in the legend of Tannhäuser.

And here is the remarkable reply provided by Piccolomini. In the beginning, he is doubtful and perplexed:

«I replied to him that I knew a Harbour of Venus, also called of Venerius, which is near Luni amidst the mountains of Liguria, where I spent three nights when I was on my journey to Basel. Furthermore, I know a mount in Sicily named Erice, which is consecrated to Venus; however I have never heard that in those places magical arts are taught».

[In the original Latin text: «Dixi me scire portum Veneris. Alii venerii dicunt qui est prope lunam inter Ligusticos montes, quo in loco tres noctes egi dum Basileam peterem. Inveni etiam apud siculos montem fore, qui Herix appellatur, Veneri sacer. Sed in his locis nihil accepi magicum tradi»].

But then the learned Italian scholar is stricken by a reminiscence:

«In discussing the subject, it came to my mind that there is a lake, in Umbria - which is known as the province of the Duchy - not far from the town of Norcia, where a craggy mountain opens into a huge cavern, through which the running waters flow. I remember I once heard that witches are found there and fiends and nocturnal wraiths; there those who house a bold heart can hear the voices of fiendish spirits, and talk to them and learn from them the magical arts».

[In the original Latin text: «Inter conferendum autem venit in mentem lacum esse in umbria, quae provincia ducatus dicitur, non longe ab Urbe Nursia ubi preruptus mons ingentem speluncam facit per quam aquae

fluunt. Illic memini audisse me striges esse et demones ac nocturnas umbras, ubi qui audaces animo sunt, spiritus nequam audiunt, alloquunturque et artes ediscunt magicas»].

Fig. 3 - The words written by Enea Silvio Piccolomini's letter on the mountain and lake lying in the vicinity of Norcia (Italy)

This letter provides an independent confirmation of the fact that in the fifteenth century the Lake of Pilatus and the Sibyl's Cave were known within a distinguished milieu of highly-educated scholars and men of letters. And the renown was not founded only on the presence of an oracular Sibyl: that was a place where black magic was being practiced, and the rumours about this peculiar feature were already running, at that time, throughout Europe.

This text is no new finding: Pio II's letter has been published more than once, and in modern times it was presented by Giuseppe Santarelli in his book "Legends of the Sibillini Mountain Range" (1974 - 1979).

However, Santarelli could not rely on the text contained in the manuscripted version: he could only quote from the version printed in 1551 in Basel. And this printed version contains a few errors.

So, by continuing our perusal of the original manuscript of Pope Pius II's letter, we will find a few fresh new findings, that only "The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend" is able to present with this paper to a wider audience.

2. A lake, a mountain and a cavern: handling a highly-sensitive topic with the utmost care

When, in the first half of the fifteenth century, Enea Silvio Piccolomini, a prominent member of an illustrious Italian family from Tuscany, a cardinal of the Roman Church and a learned scholar, received a visit of a person who asked him for information on black magic, he became cautious to the greatest degree. In his position, this might have turned into an explosive matter, should the letter he was putting down fall into the wrong hands.

So, when we read his words today, we can sense all his circumspection in writing his letter to 'his brother' Gregory. He knows how to help his visitor, he knows about the gloomy fame of Mount Sibyl and the Lakes of Pilatus, the places where sorcery is practiced through the summoning of evil entities; yet he says he has a mere 'reminiscence' of it, he just 'once heard'

about all that. And, for good measure, he adds the following words (see figure):

«I have never witnessed facts of that sort, nor have I ever cared to; since what is apprehended only through sin, it is much safer not to know at all».

[In the original Latin text: «haec non vidi, nec vidisse curavi. Nam quod peccato discitur melius est ignorasse»].

Fig. 4 - A composite picture showing the Lakes of Pilatus and Mount Sibyl in Italy, with the sentence written by Enea Silvio Piccolomini in his letter stating he had no personal experience of magical arts

All that said, it is clear that cardinal Piccolomini does not want to simply dismiss his important visitor, the servant of an illustrious personage, sent to him by «a prominent Saxon astronomer» who is «craving for magic». He is so eager to please the scholar's assistant that he entrusts him to his correspondent, jurist Gregory, by sending the distinguished astronomer's servant from Carinthia, Austria to Siena in Italy (we will see later in this article for what reason Enea Silvio is in Austria, and the true personal details of Gregory), together with his own letter and a few stringent recommendations:

«In fact in this matter your kindness would be highly appreciated by myself too, because the man who sent this herald to me is the physician of the Duke of Saxony, a person as illustrious as powerful».

[In the original Latin text: «Nam et ipse mihi et tu in hoc rem gratissimam facietis, is enim qui nuntium hunc mittit medicus est ducis Saxoniae, homo tum dives tum potens»].

But why should the astronomer's and physician's assistant travel to Siena? Piccolomini intends to arrange a rendezvous between the astronomer's herald and another man from Siena, possibly an elderly scholar, who may possibly provide further information on the magical cavern and lake:

«Despite my scarce knowledge of the topic, Savinus, the man proficient in civil law who owns a house amid the public lodging houses in the district of the Porta Camollia [editor's note: a gate in the walls of Siena], he assured me that all such things are true, he once mentioned to me the name of the lake and also provided a description of the place; however, the whole matter has now long vanished from my memory, which is slicker than eels: so I kindly ask you, if Savinus is still alive, to take this man to his presence and entrust him to Savinus».

[In the original Latin text: «Sed Savinus iuris civilis peritus qui apud Camillinam inter publica diversoria domum habuit, haec mihi vera esse asseveravit, lacum nominavit et locum descripsit, sed ista ex memoria fugerunt, quae labilior est anguillis: ideo te rogo, si Savinus vivit, hunc virum ut ad se ducas sibi eum commendes»].

The future Pope, in his letter, openly professes his ignorance on the Italian mountain where black magic is practiced and claims he has no interest neither in knowing nor in remembering.

But let's think it over: would you ever tell an important person to travel from Austria to Italy and meet an elderly man just for the sake of a mere fairy tale? Would you really send a guy, who works for a distinguished scholar, a physician of a Duke, into a futile, unproductive journey? Would you play such a trick to the trustworthy servant of «a person as illustrious as powerful»?

Of course, no chance. Enea Silvio Piccolomini, at that time an Imperial secretary and a clever diplomat, knew perfectly well what he claimed he could but hardly remember, the information that seemed to be «slicker than

eels» in his memory. He was more than certain that the tale about the cavern and lake was true. He believed in the story of Mount Sibyl.

On a mountain in the vicinity of Norcia, there were a cave and a lake where evil magic was employed. And that was no mere rumour. It was well worth a journey.

Fig. 5 - Enea Silvio Piccolomini in his formal papal dress as he appears in the miniature which introduces the collection of letters contained in manuscript Latin 8578

Piccolomini does not mention the noun “Sibyl”. Yet, it is clear that the place is the same described by Antoine de la Sale and Andrea da Barberino in their fifteenth-century works. And Enea Silvio stresses the point that, in that place, the main role is played by black magic. A primary, most important consideration, that we will expand in future articles.

But our research on Pius II's letter is not over yet. We still have to introduce a few additional remarks. Because many earlier scholars, who quoted from this letter with relation to the Apennine Sibyl, made a number of mistakes:

first, Silvio's actual whereabouts when he wrote the letter; secondly, the letter's date; and, finally, the identity of Gregory, the 'brother' to whom the letter is addressed.

So we will provide all the correct information on Piccolomini's letter. In the next paragraph.

3. Omissions and inaccuracies in the 1551 printed edition of Piccolomini's letter

A cardinal, Enea Silvio Piccolomini, who in 1458 became Pope with the regnal name Pius II. A letter, which he wrote when he received a visit from a herald sent to him by an illustrious personage who was the physician and chief astronomer of a German duke. The gloomy fame of Mount Sibyl, in Italy, with a cave and a nearby lake, where many knew that necromancy was being practiced. An astounding piece of evidence that the Italian mountain was everything but an ordinary place: not just one of the innumerable peaks that made up the Apennine mountain ridge, which runs across the spine of Italy.

But when was Piccolomini's letter written, and where, and to whom was it addressed?

The scholars, who in recent years have considered Piccolomini's text in their studies on the legend and lore of the Apennine Sibyl, have made a number of mistakes.

At present, the common belief is that the letter was written by Enea Silvio in 1431, on his way to the Council of Basel, which was being held in that same year; and, according to this belief, the note was addressed to Piccolomini's brother, George.

All the previous bits of information are wrong.

This misconception was originated by the fact that all scholars had not the chance to access the original manuscripted version of the letter, which we are presenting in this article; instead, they all took into consideration the

printed version published in Basel by Henrichum Petri in 1551 (see figure), which contains a number of omissions and inaccuracies.

Fig. 6 - The printed version of the Enea Silvio Piccolomini's letters published in 1551 by Henrichum Petri, with the letter 'on the Mount of Venus'

Let's consider the year and place in which the letter was written down: the printed version does not contain any reference to such details; instead, the date and place are clearly set out in the final part of the original manuscripted version (see figure):

«[...] Do as if you were me: and what you wish, I will do accordingly. Be well, my dear. Written in Sankt Veit, Carinthia, on January, 15th 1444»

[In the original Latin text: «[...] Finge te esse me: et quid tunc velles, id facito. Vale optime. Ex sancto vito carinthia die XV ianuarii M.CCCC.XXXX.IIIII»].

In 1444, Piccolomini was actually a secretary to Frederick III, the Duke of Styria, Carinthia and Carniola, in Austria, and King of the Romans, the title

that preceded the formal coronation as Holy Roman Emperor. This fact is further confirmed by the heading of the letter, where Piccolomini declares to hold a post as «Imperialis Secretarius», a position he actually did not hold in year 1431.

Fig. 7 - The final portion of Piccolomini's letter with the indication of the date and place in which the letter itself was written

The 1551 printed version contains another error as well: in the heading, it reads «to jurist George, his brother» («Georgio Iurisconsulto fratri suo», in Latin). But Enea Silvio had no such brother. For the manuscripted versions tells the reader a different story:

«... to jurist Gregory, his brother» («...Gregorio iurisconsulto fratri suo»).

The right name is not 'George', but 'Gregory', and the latter is Gregorio Lolli, a young cousin of Enea Silvio. Lolli was born in Siena and became a close friend of Enea Silvio Piccolomini when the future Pope was

eighteen and decided to settle in the Tuscan town to attend the local University. The two friends shared the same love for the study of Latin authors and classical history. Lolli took his law degree in Siena in 1441, and he was still living there when Piccolomini wrote to him his letter about the 'Venusberg' in 1444. They used to write letters to each other, and owing to their friendship and mutual respect they often addressed each other as 'my brother'.

So what does this letter tell to us? From the text of the message, we know that in 1444 Enea Silvio Piccolomini entrusted the servant of an important personage, a prominent member of the court of the Duke of Saxony, to a close friend in Siena, for the arrangement of a meeting with an old jurist, Savinus, who had a specific knowledge on the dark fame which enshrouded a mountain and a lake lying in the vicinity of Norcia. Mount Sibyl and the Lake of Pilatus.

We are now left with the difficult task to unveil the identity of the unknown Saxon astronomer, the personal physician of a Duke of Saxony. Who was he?

We could not pinpoint his name, even though the available clues are of high significance.

We know that in 1444 Saxony, a territory in northern Germany ('Sachsen' in German), was split in two areas: the Saxe-Wittenberg, ruled by Frederick II The Gentle ('Friedrich der Sanftmütige'); and Saxe-Lauenburg, ruled by Bernhard II. But they were not the only existing Dukes of Saxony, as other relatives of theirs bore the same title (for instance, Wilhelm III, Frederick's younger brother).

Did they have a personal physician and astronomer? Of course they did, just like all other upper-rank ruling aristocrats of their historical age. We have lots of names of scholars, astronomers and physicians, who lived around that period in Germany and Austria: from Johann Schindel to Johannes Müller 'The Regiomontanus', from Bernhard Walther to Georg von Peurbach, and many others. However, none seems to have been active in that exact years, of having been of Saxon origin, or having acted as personal physicians to any Saxon duke.

And the most promising name, that of Nicholas of Kues (Nicolaus Cusanus), the great German philosopher, diplomat, astronomer and physician, who was a close acquaintance of Enea Silvio Piccolomini and would have surely addressed his friend to retrieve information on a Venusberg in Italy, unfortunately seems to have nothing to do with Saxony and the dukes of Saxony.

So we have to leave to professional scholars, proficient in the history of ancient German Saxony, the impervious task of searching amid the antique papers for the identity of the Saxon Astronomer referred to by Piccolomini.

However, one fact is certain: in 1444 Mount Sibyl and its nearby lake were already notorious for being a place where necromancy was being performed. With no specific reference to any Sibyls.

This is a most important clue to a deeper understanding of the true nature of a magical mountain and lake that, in the fifteenth century, were being considered as very special places. Places worth a visit if you had a fancy for summoning demons.

Places that were possibly known for such peculiar use since much earlier times.

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